

Effect of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises' Access to Credit Services and Employment Creation on Poverty Level in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises' (MSMEs) access to credit services and MSMEs' employment creation on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria. The mixed-method research strategy was adopted. The population of this study includes; 5, 757,817 micro, small and medium enterprises in the six states of north-central Nigeria, out of which a sample size of 384 was selected. The Cochran sample size formula (1977) was employed to compute the sample size. The study adopted the use of the Ordinal Regression Method (ORM) as a method of analysis. The findings revealed that MSMEs' access to credit services has a negative impact on the poverty level in north central Nigeria and that MSMEs' employment creation has a negative and significant effect on the poverty level. The study concluded that Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in North-central Nigeria face numerous challenges that have hindered their profitability, sales performance and survival. Challenges range from poor infrastructural development, accessing credit facilities for expansion, and poor managerial skills of the MSMEs' operators etc. Therefore, the study recommended that the government should provide grants and aid to MSMEs in the North-central to ensure adequate financing of MSMEs enterprise. Also, the government should provide policies that will support and improve the creation of MSMEs in the North-central.

Key Words: Credit services, Employment creation, MSMEs, Nigeria

Introduction

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises can be defined based on people's opinions of the concept, and the definition varies from country to country. In contrast, some define MSMEs in terms of total revenue; others use the number of employees as the basis for categorization. A medium-sized enterprise has 250 employees, a small firm has less than 50 employees, and a microenterprise has a maximum of 10 employees. Small and Medium Enterprises can be defined using three qualitative criteria; the number of employees; total assets in U.S. dollars, and annual sales in U.S. dollars (Gentrit & Pula, 2015). Therefore, to qualify as an SME, the business must meet the quantitative criteria of several employees and at least one financial criterion. In Nigeria, a small enterprise has an annual turnover of less than N25 million, and a medium enterprise has an annual turnover of between N25 million to N100 million (Onyejekwulum, 2019). From the above, it can be summarized that the parameters for defining MSMEs include; capital investment in plant and machinery, the number of workers employed and volumes of production or turnover of the business. Micro, Small and Medium

Enterprises (MSMEs) performance in this study is equated to the poverty level as a result of MSMEs activities.

Growing the MSMEs sector has been the concern of every government, most especially in developing countries. The Sustainable Development Goals' (SDG) projection was to eradicate poverty by 2030, and one of the practical ways to achieve this feat is for the government, international agencies and other philanthropists to look for ways to support the massive creation, growth and development of the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) sector due to its importance as a catalyst of industrial growth, employment generation, poverty reduction and human capital development (SMEDAN, 2018). The MSMEs are an important part of the business landscape in any country, but they are faced with many challenges that inhibit their ability to function and contribute greatly to the economic growth of many African countries. The position in Nigeria is not different from this generalized position.

The factors inhibiting the performance and growth of the MSMEs sector in Nigeria include; lack of access to finance, lack of workspace, lack of skilled workforce, the multiplicity of taxes, inconsistency policies, weak infrastructure, lack of entrepreneurship and vocational training, obsolete equipment, lack of access to research and development, lack of access to quality information and advice, technological disruption (that is, lack of access to technology especially for marketing of products) and high cost of doing business, among others (NBS, 2018). MSMEs' growth is affected by several problems, some of which include; a low-income base, inadequate market research, lack of business strategy, inexperience, cut-throat competition, as well as inadequate entrepreneurial skills. Also, access to capital, poor operating environment and high illiteracy rate remain limiting factors. (Bessell, 2015).

This gap in finance for MSMEs operating in Nigeria is about N617.3 billion annually before the advent of the coronavirus pandemic (CBN, 2018). In 2018, less than 1% of the total commercial credit went to the MSMEs sector (Bessell, 2015); while not up to 5% of MSMEs' owners were able to access the required finance for working capital and business expansion through the sector was still able to contribute about 50% to the country's GDP.

Lack of access to finance coupled with the neglect or less attention given to empowering the female population of the country are parts of the reasons for the endemic poverty in Nigeria. Women account for about 49% of the total population of Nigeria; one out of every four women in sub-Saharan Africa is a Nigerian; 41% totalling 23 million micro-business owners in Nigeria are women; women own 20% of enterprises in the formal sector while 12% of directors of corporate organizations are women (PwC, 2020). Therefore, not giving women the same opportunity given to men is also a significant contributing factor to poverty.

Poverty is a deep-rooted, endemic and multifaceted phenomenon. Poverty can be regarded as the oldest and most significant prevalent ailment that has brought a destructive scourge on the growth and development of most countries, especially the world's developing countries. This epidemic has killed more people than the world-known diseases such as Coronavirus, HIV, Ebola, and Malaria,

despite the considerable amount of resources and programmes of every government and international organizations to eradicate and alleviate poverty and its devastating effects on society (Addae-Korankye, 2014). Poverty is one of the major impediments to achieving the Millennium Development Goals (MDG), especially in developing countries (UNDP, 2017). The factors responsible for high-level poverty, especially in developing countries, include; risky rural life, high population growth, fragile and conflict-afflicted states, lack of education, good health care and skills, little or no public investment in agricultural research, extension, irrigation and rural infrastructure and the continued inequality between men and women (World Bank, 2019).

Extreme poverty is absolute in Nigeria as a good proportion of the country's population can hardly afford the necessities of life such as food, clothing, good health care, shelter, education and other fundamental infrastructures to live an everyday life (Voelwoen, 2018). The effect of this has made the life expectancy of an average Nigerian to be shorter, led to high infant mortality rate and high rate of women dying during child-birth as there are no hospitals to provide basic health care facilities to the teeming population, especially those in the rural areas. There is high level of illiteracy because of the near collapse of the educational sector and laxity on the part of the Government in enforcing the Universal Basic Education Scheme, also the inability of the majority of the populace to send their wards to private Institutions (WPC, 2019). Due to all these, Nigeria is confronted with myriad of social and political upheavals that have destroyed and brought the country to its knees. Now, the country is faced with the activities of internet fraudsters, kidnapping, and insurgency, especially in the Northern part and all other militant group in the Niger Delta.

An individual is considered multidimensionally poor if denied access to at least one-third of the weighted gauge for measuring multidimensional poverty; years of schooling, child's school attendance, child mortality, nutrition, electricity, improved sanitation, improved drinking water, flooring, cooking fuel and asset ownership. The cut-off point for poverty was 33.33%, but out of the entire population of Nigeria, 17.5% are vulnerable to poverty, 32.8% are in severe poverty, and 34.6% are destitute (OPHI, 2019). Combating poverty with its attendant effects on crime and other social ills has been one of the major concerns of every individual, government, and world international agency.

Since Nigeria attained independence in 1960, considerable efforts have been made toward industrial growth. The government's earlier attempt to industrialize Nigeria was directed towards establishing large-scale industry. Still, recent attention has pointed to growing the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in line with the positive results recorded with such strategy by Asian countries, which accounted for their rapid economic growth (Babajide, 2012). From the layout of the first, second, third and fourth National Development plans of many years, the spotlight was on government-driven industrialization articulated on import- substitution strategy, which, when confronted with the global recession of 1981-1985, uncovered the fragility of the nation's industrial composition and design (OPHI, 2019).

Furthermore, despite the establishment of the Nigerian Industrial Development Bank (NIDB) in 1964 from the restructured Investment Company of Nigeria (ICON) to boost and accelerate the

industrial development of Nigeria through the provision of finance for the industrial project among other objectives, Nigeria's industrial development master plans did not possess the required ingredients to avert the social economic upheavals such as economic deficits, abundant poverty, unemployment and insecurity of lives and properties. Therefore, due to this, there was a continuous insistence on test-running other development plan alternatives that could probably activate economic prosperity for the country; this position was also supported (Luciano, 2018).

The introduction of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) of the International Monetary Fund (IMF) in 1986 was seen as an alternative to resolve the ineffectiveness and inefficiencies of the earlier National Development Plan Initiatives. The Structural Adjustment Programme's (SAP) objective was to ensure the liberalization of the economy by advancing investment in the real sector through encouraging non-oil sector exports and preparing the ground for private sector to take off with its attendant effects to stimulating efficiency and growth of the country's industrial sector as well as the evolution and application of domestic raw materials, as opposed to foreign and/or imported ones (Akoja & Balcioglu, 2010). Since the adoption of SAP in 1986, attention has shifted from a government-driven economy system to a private sector-driven economy, especially the growth of the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises because of its critical role as the primary contributor to the creation of wealth and employment, promotion of the growth and utilization of local raw materials, increase in export and foreign exchange earnings, socioeconomic growth as well as human capacity development (Ilori, Ile & Allen-Ile, 2018).

Because of this very important role, the governments of Nigeria in 1984 and 1986 negotiated, got into an agreement and obtained loans of US\$41 million and US\$270 million, respectively, from the World Bank, in what was termed the World Bank SME Loan Schemes 1 and 11 (John & Ebri, 2021). In 2010, the Central Bank of Nigeria established the N200 billion Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) Credit Guarantee Scheme (SMECGS) to ensure the growth and access to credit by the SMEs in Nigeria; also in 2013, the Central Bank of Nigeria launched the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Development Fund (MSMEDF) to provide low-interest finance to MSMEs sub-sector of the Nigerian economy.

Also, to guarantee the regular and easy flow of capital to aid the operations of the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises operators in Nigeria, successive governments have developed progressive programmes and strategies directed at the sector (Nwosu & Ochu, 2017). From 1960-1970, the government established Industrial Development Centres throughout the length and breadth of the country; in 1971, the Small-Scale Industries Credit Guarantee Scheme was created to propel development by making credit available from banks to SMEs and Manufacturers. The Nigerian Industrial Development Bank (NIDB) was founded in 1964 with the charge of providing long-term capital for investment and industrial activities. In 1972, the Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI) was established to assist the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) by providing long-term investment and equity funds.

The merger of the Nigerian Industrial Development Bank (NIDB), Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI), and the National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) in the year 2001 gave birth to the current Bank of Industry (BOI), which is the largest Development Finance Institution in Nigeria. The aim of the merger and for setting up the Bank of Industry (BOI) was to

properly situate the Bank to attend to the country's failing industrial growth by providing financial support for the creation of new enterprises, rejuvenation, modification, diversification and enlargement of the old and existing enterprises, and, overhauling of the ailing enterprises (BOI, 2018). The Bank, to catalyze the industrial growth of the country, opened offices and planted representatives in all the states of the federation, including the Federal Capital Territory. The management of the Bank committed over 85% of the bank resources to SME financing, collaborated with the state governments to organize entrepreneurship orientation programmes, and assisted businesses; that added value to domestic raw materials, improved employment generation and could guarantee export. The Bank also built a relationship with local and international development organizations such as UNDP, UNIDO, SMEDAN, among others (Nwosu & Ochu, 2017).

The Bank developed products to cater to the market's needs Women and Children, Youths, especially those undergoing the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC), Farmers, Manufacturers/Producers, Artisans and other categories of customers. In 2007, the Bank of Industry started the State Matching Fund Scheme, which involved contributions from both the state governments and other private persons to catalyze the industrial development of the country. The move aimed at creating wealth so people could have access to funds for their investments, thereby creating employment opportunities that would invariably ensure poverty reduction and/or eradication. The Bank (BOI) also has a programme for funding cooperative societies using the micro-credit funding scheme.

Furthermore, since the return to democratic rule, the Government of Nigeria has been concerned about diversifying the country's economy and growing the MSMEs sector (SMEDAN, 2018). Some strategic moves by the Government of Nigeria involve the formation of the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency (SMEDAN), execution of the National Enterprise Development Programme (NEDEP), formation of the National and State Councils for the Small and Medium Enterprises, YOUWIN, and other funding opportunities provided by the Central Bank of Nigeria and some development banks (CBN, 2018).

Other attempts by the Government at growing the MSMEs sector and alleviating poverty in the MSMEs' survival funds of N75 billion by the Federal Government in 2023 in order to cushion the effect of the coronavirus pandemic (Covid-19) on businesses, the signing into law the Finance Act 2020 that exempts MSMEs of below N25 million actual turnover from paying taxes, the signing of the CAMA 2020 amendment act, and the Executive order of the ease of doing business (SMEDAN, 2018).

To ensure the inclusion of women in business, the Bank of Industry and some commercial banks created some special credit programmes to support female entrepreneurs; the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Development (FMWASD) created a N90 million - Business Development Fund for Women (BUDFOW), the aim was to grant soft loan to female entrepreneurs. Also, there is the Goldman Sachs for 10,000 Women meant to provide women entrepreneurs with business and management education, mentoring and networking, and access to capital as well as the women network group such as the Women in Management, Business and Public Service (WIMBIZ) which is also aimed at providing networking and business education to women (SMEDAN, 2018).

In the same vein, the government of many countries, especially developing countries, set up or collaborate with Development Finance Institutions (DFIs) to grow the real sector of the economy.

Development Finance Institutions are multilateral, regional or bilateral institutions created to provide a platform to cover the investment deficits of evolving countries' Development Finance Institutions invest in sectors where the market has been neglected or where governmental or corporate failures exist. They give long-term advances and loans with the capacity to even restructure such loans and advances to pave the way for a more convenient payback mechanism. With this, Development Finance Institutions (DFIs) can encourage industries regeneration, development of economies, diversification of sectors, inclusive and prosperous enterprise growth, and societal and economic objectives, which are pre-qualifications for the all round economic goals of the country (Babajide, 2012).

Despite this attention and massive investment by the Federal, State and Local Governments, multilateral organizations and philanthropists are also on the forefront to reduce the level of poverty in the country through the creation of so many avenues for MSMEs owners to access finance, especially with the formation of the Bank of Industry and opening of many branches in all the zones of the country.

The rate of growth of MSMEs in North-central Nigeria is still being hampered by access to finance as many of them (MSMEs) in the region do not have the required capital to either begin or grow their businesses and achieve the required level of economic diversification (Sanni, Oke, & Alayande, 2020).

This is mainly due to higher transaction costs of accessing a loan, untidy record keeping (especially accounting records), ineffective management, illiteracy and poor financial and investment management (Okere, Njoku, & Nwosu, 2020). Therefore, North-central Nigeria is still ravaged by a high-level poverty rate and low-level industrialization, compared to other regions in the country, especially the Southern regions, as many households still earn income below what is required to maintain basic living standards (Ndanusa, 2017). This research, therefore, examined Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) financing and poverty level in North-central Nigeria. The study will essentially consider whether Bank of Industry (BOI) Services of Equity Financing, Funds Management, Workshop and Training, Networking, Mentorship and Monitoring, SME Consultants, Farmers Assistance, Graduate Entrepreneurship Fund, Youth Ignite Programme - short, medium and long-term finance have helped to promote an increase in the number of MSMEs' owners in the region under consideration.

This study examined the effect of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises' access to credit services and employment creation on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. ascertain the effect of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises' access to credit services on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria.
- ii. establish the effect of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises' employment creation on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria.

Literature Review

Poverty

The discussions on poverty and the priority given to the concept by individuals, Governments, whether in developed or developing nations, as well as international agencies have made it a critical concept that has remained constant, even through every successive Government, especially in developing countries, have put in place several programmes to either lessen, attenuate or eradicate its scourge in the annals of the human race (Adamu, 2019). The complexity surrounding the meaning of 'poverty' has made it challenging to have a generally accepted definition of the concept. Different schools of thought have come up with several reports of the word poverty (Odunjo-Saka, Adegboyega, Omotola & Akanni, 2021).

Poverty can be explained in several dimensions (Tsouli, 2022). Though classically, the word 'poverty' is used in connection with income, such beliefs still exist even to date. A person's inability to possess the fund to meet the basic needs of life was seen as poverty. The notion can be traced to the 19th century, in which the mentality then was having a means of livelihood. However, there is a change in orientation regarding viewing poverty from the monetary perspective to include expanded variables such as political participation and social inclusion (Sanchez-Martinez & Davis, 2014). Poverty can be defined as the failure of a person to reach the least standard of living, which can be viewed as the inability to afford the basic needs of life such as food, clothing, good health care, shelter, clean water, education and other fundamental infrastructures to live a normal life (Tsouli, 2022).

However, critically examining what poverty means depends on who asks the question, how it is understood and who responds. This can be explained from five different interrelated perspectives. The first is income poverty, which can also be referred to as consumption poverty for ease of measurement; this is the economists' perspective on poverty. The second is material lack or want; this refers to the inability to possess basic physiological needs of life such as good food, shelter, clothing, television or radio, or the means to move from one place to the other and means to quality services. The third is capability deprivation. Which explains what a person can or cannot do and be. It goes beyond material incapability or desire to incorporate human accomplishments such as skills, physical potential, and self-esteem among the community.

The fourth encompasses a predominantly complicated perspective of impoverishment, with the three earlier discussed as physical yardsticks to measure the poverty level. The Fourth explanation of the word 'poverty' is the proclamation of one's level of education, training, psyche, exposure, and ruminations. This underscores the intellectual capabilities to make judgments in line with one's knowledge (UNDP, 2017). The fifth perspective of poverty is being poor, marginalized, vulnerable, excluded or deprived. Therefore, being poor entails all of the above, and all efforts at alleviating poverty have yielded minimal results. Even if people are provided with the necessities of life, their level of reasoning, exposure, and judgments are major concerns. This means any attempt to reduce poverty must be all-encompassing to incorporate all the above perspectives. (UNDP, 2017).

An individual is considered multidimensionally poor if denied access to at least one-third of the weighted gauges for measuring multidimensional poverty. These are; years of schooling, child's school attendance, child mortality, nutrition, electricity, improved sanitation, improved drinking water, flooring, cooking fuel and asset ownership (OPHI, 2017). Poverty can also be explained as a

relative term than an absolute term, and poverty is more of the inability of people to be warmly accepted into the community than a lack of income (Sule, S. Y. Ibrahim & A. Ibrahim, 2018). Therefore, poverty can be relative or absolute (UNESCO, 2017). Absolute poverty concerns the quality of life or the extent of disparity in the community. It implies the money available to afford the requirements of good food, clothing, and shelter but is silent on the fact that every person has critical social and cultural obligations.

Poverty in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the actual state of poverty is still controversial among researchers, policymakers, data analysts, and the political class. While some researchers think that poverty has reduced drastically as a result of several deliberate efforts put forward by the government, some do not agree with such an assertion as they claim that the level of poverty in the country is still very high. However, others want answers to be provided on the actual percentage increase or decrease in the poverty level of the country (World Bank, 2018). Data from the Harmonized Nigeria Living Standards Survey (HNLSS) and Nigeria General Household Survey 2015-2016 affirmed that the country's official poverty rate is unreasonably on the rise, with over sixty-one per cent of the population living below the poverty line (World Bank, 2018).

The latest report from the World Poverty Clock indicated that the country's poverty level is very high, with over ninety-one million Nigerians impoverished (WPC, 2019). Therefore, poverty is one of Nigeria's fundamental challenges, as indicators from both local and international research viewed poverty as a real hindrance to the country's socioeconomic development (Voelwoen, 2018). Despite the several poverty alleviation programmes put in place by successive Nigerian governments, there has not been any worthwhile improvement in Nigeria's Human Development Index as the country is still confronted with a high level of youth unemployment which is responsible for the rate of violence, crime and other social ills of different kinds (WPC, 2019).

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Financing in Nigeria

Defining Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises is extremely difficult and contentious, as no universally accepted definition exists. This is because the definition varies in terms of peoples' opinions of the concept and from one country to the other. At the same time, some define it in terms of total revenue while others use the number of employees as the basis for categorization (John-Akamelu, & Muogbo, 2018). For example, European Union defines a medium-sized enterprise as one with 250 employees, a small firm with less than 50 employees and a microenterprise with a maximum of 10 employees.

From the World Bank's perspective, Small and Medium Enterprises can be defined using three qualitative criteria; (1) the number of employees; (2) total assets in U.S. dollars and (3) annual sales in U.S. dollars; therefore, to qualify as a SMEs in line with the World Bank standard, the business must be able to meet the quantitative criteria of several employees and at least one financial criterion (Gentrit, & Pula, 2015). The Nigeria Finance Bill 2019 considered a small enterprise as one with an annual

turnover of less than N25 million, while a medium enterprise has an annual turnover of between N25 million to N100 million (Onyejekwulum, 2019).

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) can formally seek financial help from banks (commercial, merchant, and development), even though the Nigerian financial system views them as a weak sector, making them reluctant to lend to them. The Bank would rather pay the penalty for not providing credit to MSMEs than risk extending a loan to them (Adekoya, 2021). Therefore, owners' savings and support from banks, government institutions, local governments, cooperative organizations, relatives and friends, and moneylenders are all sources of investment capital for SMEs. However, most research claimed that personal savings were the primary funding source for MSMEs.

Theoretical Review

The theoretical background for this study is the classical theory. According to Classical traditions, poverty is the consequence of the choices made by individuals (Brady, 2019). This view is traceable to Adam Smith and David Ricardo, the 17th, 18th, and 19th centuries classical economic theory of value and distribution. The theory states that the value of a product depends mainly on its cost of production and distribution. Therefore, the exchange of goods and services occurring in the marketplace directly rewards individuals' productivity, which presupposes that poverty is a direct consequence of individuals' actions and choices. A poor person is said to have made wrong choices and lacks self-control which must have inversely affected productivity. However, the classical theorists also recognized that hereditary factors might be responsible for poverty, but much emphasis was placed on wrong choices as this breeds poverty.

Therefore, the precondition for poverty can be viewed from the perspective of individuals trying to make choices and investments mainly based on information to maximize their prosperity (well-being) (Fate Foundation and BudgIT, 2020). In doing this, some individuals opt for short-term and low-payoff returns, which might be responsible for their poverty. For instance, some people made choices not to seek formal education, both at the basic and advanced levels, based on excuses best known to them. Also, some might forgo the required training that may guarantee a good pay job for them, especially in the future. These choices aggravate the conditions of individuals experiencing poverty and perpetuate it. The classical school of thought considered poverty from two perspectives; Behavioural/ decision-based theory and the sub-culture of poverty.

The Behavioural theory of poverty is based on the fact that individuals are products of their economic decisions. Therefore, people experiencing poverty should be held accountable for their actions which are direct results of their choices. This notion is based on the theory of individualism embedded in the American value and belief system, which is predominantly based on the free-market philosophy (Hampton & Varnum, 2020). The system places the success or otherwise of an individual on the person's hard work and ability to possess the basic needs of life such as food, shelter and health care services. The Behavioural/Decision-Based theory absolves the government, market forces and any external force(s) as factors responsible for the poverty level of individuals.

Empirical Review

Gbadebo, Ayofe, Olatunji & Joseph (2021) assessed the relationship between poverty alleviation programmes, unemployment, and economic development in Nigeria, which was investigated using time series data from the Central Bank of Nigeria and analyzed using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL), co-integration approach, and the Vector Auto regression (VAR) model. Considering the scope of the study, the findings revealed that poverty alleviation programmes had a significant positive effect on Nigeria's economic development, whereas unemployment was adversely significant.

Onwuka (2021) investigated the relationship between poverty, income inequality, and economic growth in Nigeria empirically with time series data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin between 1981 and 2019. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller test, Co-integration test, and Error Correction approach were used in the work. The findings in the work revealed that income inequality has a negative correlation with economic growth, whereas poverty has a positive relationship with growth in the country. The study recommended that the government should develop an all-encompassing strategy and programme that would target the poor and provide numerous possibilities to improve their well-being.

Okere, Njoku and Nwosu (2020) investigated why banks in Nigeria are hesitant to give credit facilities to SMEs. They adopted a theoretical method, and it was discovered that banks are willing and capable of providing the required cash to SMEs, but several problems have prevented them. To compensate for shortcomings in public infrastructure, SME operators must provide their energy, water, and, in some situations, access roads. This harms manufacturing viability and efficiency, and banks view it as a high-risk situation. As a business concern, banks must produce a profit and maintain sufficient liquidity to meet other stakeholders' commitments. The deposit money banks' failure to give the necessary credit to SMEs is attributable to the hostile environment in which these businesses operate. As a result, the study suggests that the government should thoroughly follow the Indian model of SME development. Again, the government should enhance the business environment in Nigeria, particularly in terms of electricity generation, long-term water supply, and good roads.

Obiwuru (2019) who carried out an exploratory research based on a secondary research method on poverty elevation amidst poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria, revealed that arbitrary programmes/policies, corruption and mismanagement, deceit on the part of the World Bank and IMF, impersonation of other countries' policies without adequate study of the applicability to the Nigerian society/system, political treachery, and intrusion, and other factors are responsible for the spate of poverty in the country despite various poverty alleviation programmes. The study suggests, among other things, that while the government dispenses funds for poverty eradication in the country, it should also carry out frequent monitoring of how the funds are being dispensed.

Abdullah and Ersoy (2018) investigated the problems confronting the development of SMEs in Turkey and Malaysia. They identified the three significant variables affecting the growth of SMEs in the selected countries as financial assistance, the impact of the knowledge-based economy and the impact of marketing assistance. Secondary data and a literature review were employed to analyze these variables. The findings revealed that both countries have been affected by the same problems, though they differ in degree. The study recommended that for the rapid growth of the SMEs, the Governments of both countries should mobilize all resources at their disposal to assist in financing the SMEs, which can be achieved by creating the required avenue for SMEs' owners to have access to bank loans, increase the education on export credit assurance system and venture capital, increase the awareness on

the use of technology, and assist in terms of research. Also it proffered that, SMEs should be trained in basic management, accounting and marketing principle

Methodology

The mixed-method research strategy was adopted. The population of this study includes; all the 5, 757,817 micro, small and medium enterprises in the six states of north-central Nigeria, out of which a sample size of 384 was selected, as well as the staff of the Bank of Industry in the six states under consideration and the Head office in Lagos. To compute the sample size, the Cochran sample size formula (1977) was employed. The data collection methods used for this study were; participatory observation, in-depth interviews, online surveys, telephone surveys and a well-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire contained closed-ended questions that were designed in such a way that enables the researcher to get accurate information from the respondents in line with the research questions. A copy of the questionnaire was given to the experts for item validation before being administered. The questionnaire was also presented to some Bank of Industry’s officials for face and content validation of the items.

The study adopted the use of the Ordinal Regression Method (ORM) as a method of analysis to examine the effect of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises’ access to credit services and employment creation on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria.

Model Specification

Poverty level = f(MSMEACS, MSMEEC). An estimable form of the above model will be given as:

$L(P) = \alpha + \beta_1(AC) + \beta_2(EC) + \mu$ Therefore, the model is specified as;

$$\text{Log } h_0(t) = \alpha(t) + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + u \dots\dots\dots$$

Where:

X takes the form of x_1 and x_2 .

i is a subscript for observation

Xs' are the covariates

α is a constant that represents the log baseline and

Log $h_0(t)$ takes a binary form, 1 if death occurs and 0 if death does not occur.

$\beta =$ is the vector of parameters to be estimated.

The predictor variables are given as x_1, x_2 ;

Where

x_1 , = MSMEs access to credit services

x_2 , = MSMEs employment creation

$\mu =$ Error term

A priori, $\beta_1 > 0$; $\beta_2 > 0$;

Therefore, the model for investigating the effect of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises' access to credit services and employment creation on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria can be written in a functional form, as shown below:

Poverty level = f(Access to credit services, MSME Employment creation)

L.P. = f(A.C., E.C.).....(i)

L.P. = The dependent variable "poverty level" is a function of MSMEs' Access to credit services and MSME Employment creation.

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 1: Presentation of Demographic Information

Variables	Characteristics	Frequency	Age (%)
Gender	Male	174	45.6
	Female	210	54.4
	Total	384	100.0
Educational Qualification	Primary	46	11.9
	ND/HND	171	44.6
	B.SC	141	36.8
	MSC	26	6.7
	Total	384	100.0
Marital Status	Single	50	13.0
	Married	324	84.4
	Divorced	10	2.6
	Total	384	100.0
Age Distribution	18-30 years	98	25.5
	31-43 years	204	53.1
	44-46 years	72	18.7
	57 years and above	10	2.7
	Total	384	100.0
Enterprise	Micro	49	12.8
	Small	222	57.8
	Total	384	100.0
	Personal savings	27	7.0
	Family Support	89	23.3
A loan from Cooperative	226	58.8	
A loan from BOI	42	10.9	

It was observed that 210 respondents, who represent about 54.4% of the respondent analyzed in the study, are female, while 174 respondents, who represent about 45.6.9% are male. It can also be observed that 46, which represents about 11.9%, possessed primary education, 171(44.6%) respondents possessed a Nigeria Certificate of Education (NCE) or Higher National Diploma (HND); 141(36.8%) of the respondents are Bachelor of Science (B.Sc) holders, 26 (6.7%) of the respondents are Masters holders.

These results implies that the majority of the respondents who are owners of the business venture have ND/HND 171(44.6%), followed by respondents having BSC 141(36.8%), while the least MSC holders had the least number of respondents in study 26(6.7%). It was observed that 50 of the respondents representing about 13% are single while 324 of the respondents which represent about 84.4% are married and 10 (2.6%) of the respondents are divorced. This implies that the study captures more married.

As observed in Table 1, 98 of the respondents, which represent about 25.5%, are within the age range of 18 years and 30 years old, while 204 of the respondents, which represent about 53.1% of the

respondents, are between 31 years of age and 43 years old. 72 (18.7%) of the respondents are between the age of 44 years and 56 years old, and 10 (4.9%) of the respondents are 57 years and above. This result implies that the majority of the respondents captured in the study area are of the younger generation who are more involved in SMEs, when compared with the older generation. As observed in the table, 49 of the respondents, which represent about 28.8% of the respondents, are micro-owners of SMEs firm, while 222 of the respondents, which represent about 57.8% of the respondents, are the small owners of SMEs, and 113 (29.4%) of the respondents are the medium owner of SMEs. This result implies that the majority of the respondents captured in the study are small owners of different SMEs business. From the table, 27 (7%) of the respondents raise money through their savings for their MSMEs business, 89 (23.3%) of the respondents raised money through family support for their business, 226 (58.8%) of the respondents raised money through cooperative societies while 42 (10.9%) of the respondents source money through the Bank of industry. It can be deduced from the above that majority of the respondents finance their MSMEs business through loans from cooperative societies.

Table 2: The main business activity

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Manufacturing	51	13.3
Accommodation and food service activities	28	7.3
Fashion, Beauty and Personal Care Industry	123	32
Agriculture	182	47.4
Total	384	100.0

Source: Research Survey, 2023

Table 4 revealed the main business activities of MSMEs used for the analysis. It can be deduced from the above table that most MSMEs' main business activity was within the agriculture sector with 182 respondents (47.4%) followed by Fashion and Beauty, with 123 respondents (32%).

Table 3: The growth of MSMEs over the last three years

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Over 20% per year	158	41
Less than 20% per year	89	23.2
Not applicable, the business is less than three years	82	21.4
No growth	34	8.9
Got Smaller	21	5.5
Total	384	100.0

Source: Research Survey, 2023

Table 5 revealed the growth of MSMEs over the past three years. It can be deduced from the above table that the majority of the MSMEs, 158 (41%), only grew by over 20% per year in the last three years.

Presentation of Data

Regression Analysis

Table 4: Regression Analysis

Parameter Estimates								
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	Df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[PL = 1.22]	-3.287	1.297	6.427	1	.011	-5.828	-.746
	[PL = 1.44]	-2.978	1.263	5.563	1	.018	-5.453	-.503
	[PL = 1.56]	-2.176	1.205	3.259	1	.071	-4.539	.186
	[PL = 1.67]	-1.241	1.169	1.126	1	.289	-3.532	1.051
	[PL = 1.78]	-.303	1.152	.069	1	.793	-2.560	1.955
	[PL = 1.89]	.533	1.155	.213	1	.644	-1.731	2.798
	[PL = 2.00]	.755	1.160	.424	1	.515	-1.518	3.029
	[PL = 2.11]	1.130	1.173	.928	1	.335	-1.169	3.429
	[PL = 2.22]	2.094	1.241	2.846	1	.092	-.339	4.526
	[PL = 2.33]	2.414	1.278	3.566	1	.059	-.091	4.920
	[PL = 2.44]	2.851	1.347	4.480	1	.034	.211	5.490
[PL = 2.56]	3.575	1.526	5.490	1	.019	.584	6.565	
Location	A.C.	-.483	.475	1.034	1	.003	1.414	.448
	TO	-.236	.648	.133	1	.001	1.506	1.034
	PR	-.478	.324	2.181	1	.000	.156	1.112
	EC	-.567	.678	6.342	1	.002	.942	1.890
	BS	.890	.321	.125	1	.610	.753	1.563
Link function: Logit.								

Source: Results 2023

Table 4 shows the ordinal regression which revealed the level of relationship among the variables of investigation. From the table, P.L. thresholds are the dependent variable while the independent variables are A.C. and E.C. The table revealed the relationship between poverty level, MSMEs' access to credit and employment creation. It can be deduced from the above regression table, that MSMEs financing has a negative impact and significant impact on the poverty level in North-

central Nigeria because the p-value of all the parameters except B.S. is less than 0.05. Statistically, a unit change or 1% change in MSMEs access to credit, turnover, profitability and job creation will bring about a 48.3%, 23.6%, 47.8%, and 56.7% reduction in the poverty level in North-Central Nigeria. Moreover, Bank of Industry business support has a positive effect on the poverty level, although it is not statistically significant. It means that the Bank of industry business support has not been so effective in supporting and financing MSMEs businesses in the North-Central which can bring about a reduction in the poverty level.

Discussion of the Findings

Table 5: Ascertain the effect of MSMEs' access to credit services on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria

MSMEs' access to credit services	SA	A	DA	SD	N	
Access to credit services has greatly influenced positively the number of MSMEs' operators in North-central Nigeria.	270 (70.3%)	105 (27.3%)	4 (1%)		5 (1.4%)	384 (100%)
The provision of cheap and affordable credit services to the MSMEs enhances their accessibility to funds and increases their income level, thereby reducing the level of poverty.	275 (71.6%)	105 (27.4%)			4 (1%)	384 (100%)

Source: Authors' computation 2023

From Table 5, it is observed that 275 (71.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that the provision of cheap and affordable credit services to the MSMEs enhances their accessibility to funds and increases their income level, thereby reducing the level of poverty in the North central of Nigeria; 105 (27.4%) also agreed that provision of cheap and affordable credit services to the MSMEs enhances their accessibility to funding and increases their income level thereby reducing the level of poverty whereas 4 (1%) of the respondents are neutral. The result implies that the majority of the respondents in the study agree that the provision of cheap and affordable credit services to the MSMEs enhances their accessibility to funds and increases their income level, thereby reducing the level of poverty in North-central Nigeria.

Moreover, it can be deduced from the table above that MSMEs' access to credit services has a negative impact on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria. A unit change in MSMEs' access to credit services will bring about a 48.3% decrease in the poverty level. Statically, the value is significant because the p-value of the parameter is less than 0.05, meaning that during the period of this

investigation MSMEs' access to credit services has significantly contributed to the reduction of the poverty level in North Central Nigeria. Thus, the null hypothesis of MSMEs access to credit services has no effect on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria and thus, is rejected, while the alternative view is accepted.

Table 6: The effect of MSMEs' employment creation on the poverty level in North central Nigeria

MSMEs employment creation	SA	A	DA	SD	N	
An increase in the number of MSMEs owners has positively affected the number of people that are gainfully employed in North-central Nigeria	241 (62.3%)	62 (16.4%)	51 (13.8%)	2 (0.4%)	28(7.1%)	384 (100%)
Due to the availability of credit facilities for MSMEs owners in North - central Nigeria, more women are gainfully employed	76 (19.8%)	233 (60.7%)	52 (13.5%)	2 (0.5%)	21(5.5%)	384 (100%)
Expansion of MSMEs can increase employment opportunities due to financing and funding	118 (30.7%)	218 (56.7)	22 (5.7%)	1 (0.3%)	25(6.6%)	384 (100%)

Source: Authors' 2023

From Table 6, it is observed that 241 (62.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed that an increase in the number of MSMEs' owners has positively affected the number of people that are gainfully employed in North-central Nigeria; 62 (16.4%) also agreed that an increase in the numbers of MSMEs owners has positively affected the number of people that are gainfully employed in North-central Nigeria while 51 (13.8%) disagreed, 2 (0.4%) strongly disagreed that an increase in the numbers of MSMEs owners has positively affected the number of people that are gainfully employed in North-central Nigeria. The result implies that the majority of the respondents in the study agree that an increase in the number of MSMEs' owners has positively affected the number of people that are gainfully employed in North-central Nigeria.

The study went further to establish the relationship between MSMEs' employment creation and poverty level. A unit change or 1% change in MSMEs employment creation will bring about a 56.7% reduction in the poverty level in North-central. Thus, the null hypothesis of MSMEs employment creation has no effect on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria and however is rejected, while the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examines the effect of MSMEs' access to credit services on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria. Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in North-central Nigeria face numerous challenges that have hindered their profitability, sales performance and survival. Challenges ranged from poor infrastructural development, accessing credit facilities for expansion, and poor managerial skills of the MSMEs operators. Above all is the unexpected outbreak of the Coronavirus outbreak (Covid-19), which had an adverse effect on the sales and performance of many MSMEs and has contributed in no small measure to the rising level of poverty in the North-central, Nigeria. The study discovered that MSMEs' access to credit services has a negative and significant impact on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria, and MSMEs employment creation has a negative and significant effect on the poverty level in North-central Nigeria.

However, the following recommendations are deemed necessary for MSMEs financing:

- i. Small and medium enterprises in North-central Nigeria should be empowered by Government through different financing means.
- ii. Provision of grants and aid by the government to MSMEs in North-central Nigeria to ensure adequate financing of MSMEs.
- iii. The government should provide policies that will support and improve the creation of MSMEs in the North-central.
- iv. There is a need for the MSMEs' owners to form a formidable association or union to be able to influence government decisions in their interest.

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